

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE
STUDY OF TERMS FOUND IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS

Mukhtoriy Mohruiy Sodirzoda

teacher of FerSU

The term is derived from the Greek word "Terminus" which means "limit", "boundary". It is a word specific to the field of science and technology, agriculture, art and culture. Terminology means the study of terms and the meaning of a set of terms. In place of the word term, sometimes there are cases of using the words term, istilah. But that's not true. A term is a narrow definition of a term. The word istilah is Arabic. People do not understand it and it has not become the norm. Issues of terminology have always been one of the most pressing issues of linguistics. Because determining the place and function of the terms in the dictionary layers of the fields allows to understand the essence of the concept correctly.

Linguist N. A. Chechlova writes in her article: "Any advanced terminology requires a high level of abstraction. Terminology consists not of a set of names of real things and actions, but of a specific system of names of concepts of things and actions. Therefore, nouns are the only lexical-semantic tools that express the concepts of objects, adjectives and actions, and nouns in the literal sense of the word come to the fore.

"Returning to the field of linguistics, we can find metaphors, metonymy, synecdoche, etc. derived from rhetoric." ¹

In all the works devoted to terminology, the units that represent certain concepts of one or another field, have a definition and mainly perform a

¹ Н.А.Щетлова, К вопросу о грамматических средствах терминологизации русских глаголов в профессиональной речи XVII-XVIII вв. – «Ученые записки МОПИ» Т. XXXVIII, вып. 8, М., 1963, стр

nominative function are considered to be terms. A.Reformatsky defines the term and concludes that "... terms are special words."

In relation to terms, updating and changing the terminological system and in improvement, it is extremely important to act in accordance with the development laws of the language, specific objective requirements of the standardization of its vocabulary system, criteria, scientific measurements and principles.

In the 30s of the 20th century, many terminological dictionaries of the Uzbek language were compiled and published. In this process, theoretical questions about the history of terms, meaning and subject groups of terms, grammatical structure and formation, the path of development and sources of enrichment were also developed. Ulug Tursunov was one of the first to try to clarify the issues of terminology of the Uzbek language and wrote works dedicated to this issue: "Against the aspirations of the bourgeoisie in linguistic terminology", "Issues of Uzbek terminology", "Issues of terminology", "Principles of choosing words and terms in the Uzbek literary language" " etc. These works reflect on various views and concepts in the field of term formation, collection, arrangement, unification and publication. In addition, it is noted that the confusions that have occurred and are occurring in the field of terminology begin to be clearly visible. For example, one concept can be translated and written in different ways; providing long explanations instead of clear and concise terms; less use of native language opportunities in term creation; It was shown that one of the sources of enrichment of Uzbek terminology is the fact of different approaches to the external factor.

In the works of Professor U. Tursunov, the rich sources of terminology of the Uzbek language are covered in detail. In his works, U. Tursunov provides information about the development of the terminological system of the Uzbek language at the expense of internal and external sources. In the development,

formation and improvement of the terminological systems of the Uzbek language, the internal capabilities of this language play a key role. Because the great changes taking place in life, the development of science and technology and culture require the maximum use of the internal capabilities of the language. As in any other language, Uzbek language uses a number of methods to express this or that concept. They consist of:

1. Enrichment of terms on account of semantic path.
2. Formation of terms by morphological method.
3. Syntactic formation of terms.

"The accuracy and strictness of the terms shows the level of science, education, and culture of this nation. The development and regulation of terms is different in different fields of science and depends on the development of a particular science. Since this development is continuous, the origin and organization of new terms is also continuous. In general, careful processing and arrangement of terms in the native language is a necessary resource for creating textbooks and manuals, as well as for teaching in the native language. The lack of processing and organization of terms also affects the style of speech.

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